

Agricultural Market Access and Economic Participation of Youth in Agricultural Entrepreneurship for sustainable livelihood in Bayelsa State

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Abstract

The study examined agricultural market access and economic participation of youth in agricultural entrepreneurship for sustainable livelihood in Bayelsa State. The study employed a descriptive research survey design. Two objectives, two research questions and two corresponding null hypotheses that were formulated and tested at significance level of 0.05 guided the study. The population of the study was 580, 216 (580,074 youth and 142 extension agents) respondents. Multistage sampling technique was used to sample 413 youth and extension agents (360 youth and 53 extension agents). The instrument for data collection was a structured Questionnaire designed in 4-point rating scale. The instrument was validated by the researcher's supervisor and three other experts. The reliability of the instrument was established using Cronbach Alpha Reliability Coefficient method which yielded a reliability index of 0.85 and 0.88. Mean and standard deviation were used to answer the research questions. The study revealed that creating agricultural market access and policies for economic participation of youth in agricultural entrepreneurship would encourage sustainable livelihood in the study area. The study recommended among others that government and other NGOs should be engaged in initiatives which support policy processes that explicitly include youth as locus of actions related to well-being, and food security. This will give youth the opportunity to create ideas that will enhance the involvement of young persons in production agriculture

Keywords: Agricultural Market, Access, Youth, Agricultural Entrepreneurship, Sustainable Livelihood

INTRODUCTION

Entrepreneurship education has risen as a viable platform to reengage rural youth in agriculture and slow rural outmigration. Students of these programs gain entrepreneurial thinking, identify business opportunities, and learn the skills to start a business, helping them see agriculture as a viable livelihood option (Morris, Webb, Fu, & Singhal, 2013). Entrepreneurship education programs focused on secondary education students, often offered through co-curricular and extracurricular platforms, can develop entrepreneurial thinking and skills (Daniel & Kent, 2005; Morris et al., 2013; Valerio et al., 2014). Yet, the characteristics of exemplary entrepreneurship programs are unknown. This worldwide review of innovative programs fills part of the knowledge gap on the phenomenon of rural youth agricultural entrepreneurship programs. This review synthesized primary and secondary historical data, gathered through internet and library searches, to summarize the state of the art in agricultural entrepreneurship education programs for rural youth around the world.

Lindiwe (2019) stated that young people must work hard in order to claim their space; they should make

themselves relevant by being informed and knowledgeable in production agriculture. They must also seek opportunities and be prepared to make sacrifices in order to achieve steady supply of food. Thus, engaging youth in agricultural industries is critical, as they represent a growing segment of the society and are quite literally, the future decision makers for sustainability. However, their involvement and interest in agricultural entrepreneurship have been low recently; and the potential entry into agricultural production has carried a host of challenges (Food Agriculture Organisation, 2014). Generally, youth worldwide have lacked motivation to enter and persist in the agricultural industry (FAO, 2014; Sharma, 2007). Agriculture according to Muir-Leresche (2013) is not seen as a viable income source and often the youth view it as employment only of last resort and may consider becoming a farmer as condemning oneself to subsistence and poverty. Even willing youth face barriers to entering agriculture such as insufficient access to knowledge, information and

education and limited access to land, financial services, green jobs, markets and engagement in policy dialogue (FAO, 2021).

Due to the evolving production and business environment in the 21st century, efforts to increase the participation of younger generations in agriculture have been increasing. These have also been driven by concerns that the continuous reliance of agriculture on the aging population, the members of which are prone to chronic diseases, could negatively affect agricultural production. In Nigeria, the average age of a farmer is reported to be 50 years (BLS 2015), while in South Africa is estimated to be about 7 years higher (Sihlobo, 2015). Furthermore, the low levels of mechanization in the small-scale enterprises that dominate Nigeria's industry renders the aging farming community an issue of great concern, as physical strength is a key asset in such enterprises. Nnadi and Akwiwu (2008) posited that the availability of able-bodied youth labour has determined the agricultural industry's output levels in the past, and it is posited that the youths' unique capabilities (dynamism, adventure, and ambition) will play a greater role in the sector's continued success in a world where there is rapid technological change. Young people have the potential to make significant contributions to agricultural development at various levels.

Agriculture seems to carry with it an image of drudgery and the option of last choice; it is often not even considered by youth in the same vein as an actual career (White, 2012). This is geared by so many factors including access to finance. Jayadatta (2017) stated that rural youths are often excluded from Nigeria credit market as they often have no physical assets for collateral. One area that needs to be seriously implemented to bring relief to rural farmers is the provision of credit facilities. The accessibility of credit facilities are important for the improvement of quality and quantity of farm produce, increase in income generation (Amadi & Aleru, 2020) and reduction of youth's migration.

The removal of marketing-related barriers has a significant role to play in motivating the participation of younger people in agricultural entrepreneurship. This is as a report from Mazeró Agrifood (MAf, 2022) that lack of organized market pose huge effect on youth involvement in agribusinesses. According to the report, majority of farmers live in villages, and as such organized markets have not developed in these rural areas for marketing of agricultural commodities to strife. So, there are no markets to supply agricultural products to the customers, no agricultural inputs to the farmers in rural areas. This therefore causes agricultural market to remain unorganized. In a study on entrepreneurial resources needs of rural farmers, Amadi and Aleru (2020) suggested the establishment of modern market specified for a particular area of agricultural commodity to boost farmers' socio-economic livelihood in the area.

The decline in the involvement of youth in agricultural-related activities could also be traced to the lack of institutional bodies to give information to the young people about the production situation, areas of distributions, price, demand and changes in price, market situation and the lucrateness in participating in agricultural marketing. This brings the exploitation of farmers by local landlords, money lenders and agro-businessmen in the agricultural marketing system. This therefore, gives reasons to establish adequate publicity on market policies in rural areas. According to MAf (2022) sufficient information should be made for the transmission of authorized prices of agricultural produce and quantity of production so that the facts relating to agricultural marketing can be put before the concerned parties.

Many young people in agribusiness lack access to reliable market information, and this result to limiting their ability to make informed decisions about production, marketing, and distribution. According to United States Agency for International Development (2018) emanate from inability of youth to have access to valuable

information that would enable them analyze the market. Without access to market information, agricultural entrepreneurs may struggle to make informed decisions about what crops to grow, how much to produce, and where to sell their products. This can limit their ability to compete in the marketplace and may discourage young people from pursuing agricultural entrepreneurship. According the International Food Policy Research Institute (IFPRI, 2019), lack of access to market information is a major constraint faced by smallholder farmers, particularly in low-income countries. This brings the exploitation of farmers by local landlords, money lenders and agrobusinessmen in the agricultural marketing system. This therefore, gives a reason for publicity of market policies.

The marketing information system distributes the relevant information to the marketers who can make the efficient decisions related to the marketing operations. This information enhances young people's decisions in pricing, packaging, development of new agricultural products, distribution, media, promotion, among others. Every marketing operation works in agreement with the conditions prevailing both inside and outside the organization, and, therefore, there are several sources (Internal, Marketing Intelligence, Marketing Research) through which the relevant information about the market can be obtained. Youth require marketing intelligence that will enable them source for information on the happenings in the market.

Agricultural marketing plays a significant role not only in stimulating food production and consumption but also in accelerating the pace of economic development. The marketing system of agriculture plays a dual role in Nigeria's economic development and countries whose resources are primarily in agricultural production. However, producers have been facing a number of problems while trying to market their agricultural goods. This has put young generation into thinking that

marketing of agricultural produce is as tedious as its production processes on drudgery method. Confirming this, Mazeró Agrifood (MAF, 2022) reported that lack of organized market poses huge effect on youth involvement in agribusinesses. According to the report, majority of farmers live in villages and as such, organized markets have not been developed in these rural areas for marketing of agricultural commodities to strife. So, there are no commercial established markets to supply agricultural products to the customers and no agricultural inputs to the farmers in rural areas thus causing agricultural market to remain unorganized.

Many young people in agribusiness lack access to market infrastructure, such as storage facilities, processing facilities, and marketplaces. This can limit their ability to add value to their products and reach wider markets (United Nations Development Programme, 2018). This prompt the assertion of Amadi and Aleru (2020) who suggested the establishment of modern market specified for a particular area of agricultural commodity. Utilizing this strategy would enable youth develop interest in production, sale and transportation of the products for sustainable livelihood.

Statement of the Problem

Bayelsa State is endowed with good climatic and soil conditions favourable for agricultural production enterprises. In spite of this, a high population of the youth who are the future of food security are constantly migrating in search of employment. Rural youth face many hurdles in trying to earn a livelihood as the challenges related to unemployment; underemployment and poverty have swamped the rural areas of Nigeria thereby creating a wide gap between citizens. A bid to bridge the gap and ensure increased economic opportunities for the rural households necessitated the adoption of agricultural entrepreneurship (Uneze, 2013). Despite the agricultural sector's ample potential to provide income-generating opportunities for rural youth in Bayelsa State, marketing related challenges often hinders youth

participation in agricultural entrepreneurship and more importantly, options for overcoming them are not extensively documented. This study therefore aims to expose strategies for enhancing agricultural market access and economic participation of youth in agricultural entrepreneurship for sustainable livelihood in Bayelsa State

Purpose of the study

The main purpose of the study was to examine the extent agricultural market access and economic participation of youth will enhance agricultural entrepreneurship for sustainable livelihood in Bayelsa State. Specifically, the study sought to

1. Ascertain the extent agricultural marketing information will enhance rural youth participation in agricultural entrepreneurship for sustainable livelihood in Bayelsa State.
2. Determine the extent removal of agricultural marketing barriers will enhance rural youth participation in agricultural entrepreneurship for sustainable livelihood in Bayelsa State.

Research Questions

The following research questions were formulated based on the objectives of the study:

1. To what extent will agricultural marketing information enhance rural youth participation in agricultural entrepreneurship for sustainable livelihood in Bayelsa State?
2. To what extent will removal of agricultural marketing barriers enhance rural youth participation in agricultural entrepreneurship for sustainable livelihood in Bayelsa State?

Hypotheses

The following null hypotheses were formulated and tested at 0.05 significance level:

1. There is no significant difference in the mean scores of youth and extension agents on extent establishment of marketing information will enhance rural youth participation in agricultural entrepreneurship for sustainable livelihood in Bayelsa State.

2. There is no significant difference in the mean scores of youth and extension agents on extent removal of agricultural marketing barriers will enhance rural youth participation in agricultural entrepreneurship for sustainable livelihood in Bayelsa State.

METHODOLOGY

The study was carried out in Bayelsa State, Nigeria. The study employed a descriptive survey research design. It involves the actual interpretation of ongoing phenomenon, existing conditions, opinions, prevailing practices, beliefs, effect that are being felt (Nworgu, 2015). Descriptive survey design is considered appropriate for this study because the study focused on identifying strategies for enhancing rural youth participation in agricultural entrepreneurship for sustainable livelihood in Bayelsa State, Nigeria. The population of the study was 580, 216 (580,074 youth and 142 extension agents) respondents. The 580,074 (18-40 years) youth from the eight (8) local government areas in Bayelsa State comprised of 311,021 male and 269,053 female youth from the study area (National Bureau of Statistics, Nigeria, 2017). The sample size for the study was 413 youth and extension agents. This was determined using the Taro Yamane method. The study adopted a multi-stage sampling technique which includes: purposive sampling technique was used to realize the sample size for the investigation and for data gathering. Four local governments (Ogbia, Kolokuma-Opokuma, Sagbama and Ekeremor) were purposively selected due to the predominance of commercial crop farming and other agricultural activities in these areas as a result of available arable lands. The study randomly selected three (3) communities each from the four Local Government Areas making a total of twelve (12) communities that were selected for the study. Thirty (30) youths were selected from each community making a total number of 360 youths that were used for the study. Finally, fifty-three (53) extension agents were randomly sampled from 142 extension agents in the

state. Therefore, the total sample size for the study was 413 respondents. The instrument that was used for this study was a self-constructed questionnaire titled “Marketing Strategies for Enhancing Youth Participation in Agricultural Entrepreneurship Questionnaire (EYPAEQ)”. The instrument contained three sections. These sections were structured on a 4-point rating scale of Very Highly Extent (VHE), High Extent (HE), Low Extent (LE), and Very Low Extent (VLE) with the value of 4, 3, 2, and 1 respectively. Validity of instrument was done by experts in Vocational and Technology Education Department in Rivers State University for face and content validation. Cronbach Alpha reliability was used to establish the reliability of the

study which gave reliability coefficients of 0.85 and 0.88; hence making the instrument reliable for this study.

Mean and standard deviation was used to answer the research questions. Items in the research questions with mean response of 2.50 and above were regarded as high extent, while those below 2.50 were regarded as low extent. Z-test statistical tool was used to test hypotheses at 0.05 level of significance.

RESULT

Research Question 1: To what extent will market information enhance youth participation in agricultural entrepreneurship for sustainable livelihood in Bayelsa State?

Table 1: Mean Responses on Extent Market Information will Enhance Youth Participation in Agricultural Entrepreneurship for Sustainable Livelihood

S/N	Statements	Extension Agents(n=53)			Youth (n=360)		
		\bar{X}_1	SD	Decision	\bar{X}_2	SD	Decision
1.	Ability to ascertain changes in the customer’s tastes and preferences will enable youth produce based on market demand for Sustainable Livelihood	3.82	0.87	High Ext	3.64	0.89	High Ext
2.	Utilization of online platforms can provide real-time market information thus enhancing youth decision in agricultural entrepreneurship for Sustainable Livelihood	3.48	0.82	High Ext	3.93	0.36	High Ext
3.	Enhancing access to youth’s information on agricultural marketing environment will boost their interest in agricultural enterprise for Sustainable Livelihood	3.90	0.66	High Ext	3.67	0.68	High Ext
4.	Availability of accurate and timely market information will enable young people to make informed decisions about production, marketing, and pricing for Sustainable Livelihood	3.14	0.81	High Ext	3.78	0.41	High Ext
5.	Utilization of social media campaigns will go a long way to boost youth access to marketing strategies thus enhancing their participation in agricultural businesses for Sustainable Livelihood	3.36	0.70	High Ext	3.25	0.81	High Ext
6.	Ability of youth to access information about the changing market trends in agricultural commodities will enable youth understand the agricultural marketing system, thus enhancing	3.81	0.72	High Ext	3.21	0.82	High Ext

	their skills in product distribution for Sustainable Livelihood						
7.	Engaging young people to agro-based institutional bodies will enhance their access to information on areas of products distributions hence motivate their interest in agro-businesses for Sustainable Livelihood	3.13	0.80	High Ext	3.51	0.96	High Ext
8.	Youth's access to information on pricing strategy will enhance their skills in market negotiation for increased income for Sustainable Livelihood	3.45	0.59	High Ext	3.16	0.59	High Ext
	Total Mean/SD	3.51	0.74	High Ext	3.59	0.69	High Ext

Field Survey, 2023

Table 1 shows the mean and standard deviation of extension agents and youth on extent market information will enhance youth participation in agricultural entrepreneurship for sustainable livelihood in Bayelsa State? It was revealed that to an extent, ability to ascertain changes in the customer's tastes and preferences will enable youth produce based on market demand for profit (3.82 and 3.64), utilization of online platforms can provide real-time market information thus enhancing youth decision in agricultural entrepreneurship (3.48 and 3.93), enhancing access to youth's information on agricultural marketing environment will boost their interest in agricultural enterprise (3.90 and 3.67), availability of accurate and timely market information will enable young people to make informed decisions about production, marketing, and pricing (3.14 and 3.78), utilization of social media campaigns will go a long way to boost youth access to

marketing strategies thus enhancing their participation in agricultural businesses (3.36 and 3.25), ability of youth to access information about the changing market trends in agricultural commodities will enable youth understand the agricultural marketing system, thus enhancing their skills in product distribution (3.81 and 3.21), engaging young people to agro-based institutional bodies will enhance their access to information on areas of products distributions hence motivate their interest in agro-businesses (3.13 and 3.51), and youth's access to information on pricing strategy will enhance their skills in market negotiation for increased income (3.45 and 3.16).

Research Question 2: To what extent will removal of agricultural marketing barriers enhance rural youth participation in agricultural entrepreneurship for sustainable livelihood in Bayelsa State?

Table 2: Mean Responses on Extent Removal of Agricultural Marketing Barrier Enhance Youth Participation in Agricultural Entrepreneurship for Sustainable Livelihood

S/ N	Statements	Extension Agents(n=53)			Youth (n=360)		
		\bar{X}_1	SD	Decision	\bar{X}_2	SD	Decision
1.	Creating direct link between farmers and markets will motivate youth's engagement in agricultural entrepreneurship for Sustainable Livelihood	3.13	0.65	High Ext	3.55	0.76	High Ext
2.	Improving rural infrastructure such as roads will help break barrier that limits youth involvement in distribution of agricultural commodities as a business for Sustainable Livelihood	3.43	0.86	High Ext	3.75	0.64	High Ext
3.	Providing tax incentives for agricultural investments will motivates young people's participation in agricultural production as a business for Sustainable Livelihood	4.23	0.71	High Ext	3.85	0.79	High Ext

4.	Providing young people with market information will enhance youth participation in agricultural product marketing for Sustainable Livelihood	4.63	1.10	High Ext	3.74	0.54	High Ext
5.	Providing training in financial management skills can help young people start and run successful agricultural businesses for Sustainable Livelihood	3.88	0.89	High Ext	3.14	1.04	High Ext
6.	Provision of market infrastructure such as storage facilities to enhance young farmers' ability to add value to their products and reach wider markets for sustainable livelihood	3.55	0.76	High Ext	3.95	0.61	High Ext
7.	Removal of policies affecting the provision of processing facilities that limit youth's abilities in value addition will enable them reach wider markets for sustainable livelihood	3.45	0.92	High Ext	3.11	0.73	High Ext
8.	Subsidizing the cost of purchasing product in agribusiness would encourage young people to embark in agribusiness for sustainable livelihood	3.75	0.84	High Ext	3.58	0.73	High Ext
	Total Mean/SD	3.35	0.84	High Ext	3.58	0.73	High Ext

Field Survey, 2023

Table 2 shows the mean and standard deviation of extension agents and youth on extent removal of marketing barriers will enhance youth participation in agricultural entrepreneurship for sustainable livelihood in Bayelsa State. It was revealed that creating direct link between farmers and markets will motivate youth's engagement in agricultural entrepreneurship (3.13 and 3.55), improving rural infrastructure such as roads will help break barrier that limits youth involvement in distribution of agricultural commodities as a business (3.43 and 3.73), providing tax incentives for agricultural investments will motivates young people's participation in agricultural production as a business (3.23 and 3.85), providing young people with market information will enhance youth participation in agricultural product marketing (3.63 and 3.74), and providing training in financial management skills can help young people develop skills needed to start and run successful agricultural businesses (3.88 and 3.14). The table also

revealed that provision of market infrastructure such as storage facilities to enhance young farmers' ability to add value to their products and reach wider markets (3.55 and 3.95), removal of policies affecting the provision of processing facilities that limit youth's abilities in value addition will enable them reach wider markets (3.45 and 3.11), and subsidizing the cost of purchasing product in agribusiness would encourage young people to embark in agribusiness (3.75 and 3.58) are various ways of removing agricultural marketing barriers to enhance youth participation in agricultural entrepreneurship for sustainable livelihood.

Hypotheses

Hypothesis 1: There is no significant difference in the mean scores of youth and extension agents on extent establishment of marketing information will enhance rural youth participation in agricultural entrepreneurship for sustainable livelihood in Bayelsa State.

Table 3: Z-Test Analysis on Extent Establishment of Marketing Information will Enhance Rural Youth Participation in Agricultural Entrepreneurship for Sustainable Livelihood

Group	N	Mean	SD	df	α	z-cal	z-crit	Decision
Extension Agents	53	3.51	0.74	411	0.05	0.80	±1.960	Accepted
Bayelsa Youth	360	3.59	0.69					

Source: Field work 2023

Table 3 summarizes the mean, standard deviations and z-test analysis of extension agents and rural youth on extent establishment of marketing information will enhance rural youth participation in agricultural entrepreneurship for sustainable livelihood in Bayelsa State. The table indicated that the Extension Agents had mean and standard deviation score of 3.51 and 0.74 respectively, while Rural Youth in Bayelsa State had mean and standard deviation response of 3.59 and 0.69 respectively. The calculated z-value obtained was 0.80, while the critical z-value stood at ± 1.960 at 411 degree of freedom on a significance level of 0.05. From the result of the analysis, it was revealed that the calculated

z-value was less than z-critical value. Thus, the null hypothesis which stated no significant difference between the mean responses of extension agents and rural youth on extent establishment of marketing information will enhance rural youth participation in agricultural entrepreneurship for sustainable livelihood in Bayelsa State was accepted.

Hypothesis 2: There is no significant difference in the mean scores of youth and extension agents on extent removal of agricultural marketing barriers will enhance rural youth participation in agricultural entrepreneurship for sustainable livelihood in Bayelsa State.

Table 2: Z-Test Analysis on Extent Removal of Agricultural Marketing Barriers will Enhance Rural Youth Participation in Agricultural Entrepreneurship for Sustainable Livelihood

Group	N	Mean	SD	df	α	z-cal	z-crit	Decision
Extension Agents	53	3.35	0.84	411	0.05	2.3	± 1.960	Rejected
Bayelsa Youth	360	3.58	0.73					

Source: Field work 2023

Table 2 summarizes the mean, standard deviations and z-test analysis of extension agents and rural youth on extent removal of agricultural marketing barriers will enhance rural youth participation in agricultural entrepreneurship for sustainable livelihood in Bayelsa State. The table revealed that the Extension Agents had mean and standard deviation score of 3.35 and 0.84 respectively, while Rural Youth had mean and standard deviation response of 3.58 and 0.73 respectively. The calculated z-value obtained was 2.3, while the critical z-value remains constant at ± 1.960 at 411 degree of freedom on a significance level of 0.05. The result revealed that the calculated z-value was less than critical z-value. Therefore, the null hypothesis which stated no significant difference between the mean responses of extension agents and rural youth on extent removal of agricultural marketing barriers will enhance rural youth participation in agricultural entrepreneurship for sustainable livelihood in Bayelsa State was rejected. This however implies that there is a significant difference in the mean responses of extension agents and rural youth on extent removal of agricultural marketing barriers will enhance rural youth's participation in agricultural entrepreneurship for sustainable livelihood in Bayelsa State.

Discussion of Findings

Findings from Table 1 showed that market information such as ability of youth to ascertain changes in

customer's tastes and preferences, utilization of online platforms to access real-time market information, enhancing access to youth's information on agricultural marketing environment, and utilization of social media campaigns to boost youth access to marketing strategies will enhance youth participation in agricultural businesses. These findings are in line with Fashoyin and Oyejisi (2021) who noted that youth participation in agriculture can be encouraged through policies and programmes that provide training, access to finance, and market information. Similarly, the findings align with MAF (2022) in a report that sufficient information is required for the transmission of authorized prices of agricultural produce and quantity of production so that the facts relating to agricultural marketing can be put before the concerned parties. Table 3 also revealed that ability of youth to access information about the changing market trends in agricultural commodities will enable youth understand the agricultural marketing system in product distribution, engaging young people to agro-based institutional bodies will enhance their access to information on value-addition and pricing strategy for increased income. This is in tandem with the assertion of Akpan and Udoh (2020) who noted that access to marketing information is crucial for agricultural entrepreneurs to make informed decisions and maximize profits. Also, the findings are line with the assertion of Bui, Donthu and Lenartowicz (2019) that utilisation of social media campaigns, influencer marketing, and interactive events will go a long way to boost youth participation in agricultural businesses. Finally, the result of the null hypothesis indicated that the responses of

extension officers and youth are significantly related on extent establishment of market information will enhance youth participation in agricultural entrepreneurship.

From Table 2, the study found out that creating direct link between youth and agricultural markets, fixing and improving rural infrastructures such as roads to break barrier that limits youth involvement in distribution of agricultural commodities, providing tax incentives for agricultural investments to encourage young people's participation in agricultural production as a business, and providing young people with access to market will enhance youth participation in agricultural product marketing are various techniques for removing marketing barriers to enhance youth participation in agricultural entrepreneurship for sustainable livelihood. The findings are in corroboration with Amadi and Aleru (2020) who in their study suggested the establishment of modern market specified for a particular area of agricultural commodity to enable farmers develop interest in production, sale and transportation of the products for sustainable livelihood. Similarly, the study is in agreement with FAO (2019) which reported that developing strong and efficient value chains through creating linkages between farmers and markets and increasing access to financing and technical assistance are essential for reducing agricultural marketing barriers. The table also found out that providing training in financial management skills to help young people develop skills needed to run agricultural businesses, removing policies affecting establishment of processing centers that limit youth's abilities in value addition and subsidizing the cost in purchasing product in agribusiness are different ways of removing marketing barriers to enhance youth participation in agricultural entrepreneurship. The findings are in line with the recommendation made by World Bank (2018) that market access will play a key role in improving the profitability of agricultural enterprises by meeting products' demand and reducing marketing costs.

CONCLUSION

Based on the findings, the study deduced that creating agricultural market access and policies for economic participation of youth in agricultural entrepreneurship would encourage sustainable livelihood in the study area. However, this would be more attractive for youth if agricultural credits are made available; and policies directed at boosting their involvement in agricultural

policy dialogue are enacted to create an enabling environment for them in agricultural sector

RECOMMENDATIONS

Based on the findings and the conclusions made in this study, the following recommendations were posited:

1. Government and other NGOs should be engaged in initiatives which support policy processes that explicitly include youth as locus of actions related to well-being, and food security. This will give youth the opportunity to create ideas that will enhance the involvement of young persons in production agriculture.
2. There is a need to implement information and communication technology training for youth to enhance their skills in accessing the right quality agricultural marketing information to improve their marketing strategies and thus meet consumers' demand.

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